

QUALITY ASSESSMENT DURING STITCHING OF REINFORCING TEXTILES FOR COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: During stitching of reinforcing textiles the stitching parameters should be set for optimal reinforcing results in the manufactured composite. The damages of the sewing thread and the reinforcing textile should be minimized. The architecture of the sewing thread should be load bearing. For optimal results measurement devices were developed which are suitable to watch the relevant parameters (presser foot distance, needle thread tension) during the stitching process. This measurement devices allow a reproducible setting of the sewing machine. A test stand for the simulation of the loads of a sewing thread is also presented which is necessary to determine the damages of the sewing thread during the stitching process.

KEYWORDS: stitching of reinforcing textiles, composites, stitching parameters, measurement, machine settings, thread damages

INTRODUCTION

Since a very long time stitching is used for joining textile parts. It is the traditional way to manufacture clothes from woven or knitted textiles. There are a lot of requirements on the stitching process during the manufacturing of clothes. But the main aim is to manufacture stitching rows which cause no buckling of the textile and possess a high elasticity. The materials and the requirements differ completely from the demands which are relevant in the area of composites. Even at non-reinforcing technical textiles, like airbags, belts and others, the requirements are not to be compared with those in the area of composites.

Stitching reinforcing textiles for composites means that a reinforcing material should be introduced in the third dimension of the textile structure. For this the sewing thread should be placed in a load bearing geometry and its damages during the stitching process should be as low as possible. The reinforcing textile should also not be damaged by the stitching process. No additional crimp should be introduced by the sewing thread.

In the past investigations of stitching reinforcing textiles have been done in America [1, 2, 3], Asia [4, 5, 6], Australia [7, 8] and Europe [9]. Nearly always stitching has been performed by using conventional sewing machines. The machine settings were fixed in a way like they would have been fixed for stitching clothes, too. Improvements of the delamination resistance, the peeling resistance and the interlaminar shear strength of the manufactured composites have been measured. In this presentation new methods for exactly reproducible settings of the sewing machines and for an instant control of the stitching process are shown.

AIMS OF STITCHING REINFORCING TEXTILES FOR COMPOSITES

A lot of methods exist for the manufacturing of composites. These methods are mainly distinguishable by the way of wetting the reinforcing textiles with the matrix material. Nearly all these methods start with the placing of layers of reinforcing textiles in a mould. In most cases woven textiles are used. These layers are bonded together by the matrix material. Most matrix materials, especially the thermoset matrix materials, are very brittle. Their mechanical properties are worse in comparison with the reinforcing materials. Therefore the reinforcement of composite materials in z-direction is poor. As a result the mechanical properties in z-direction are not as high as in-plane. In z-direction the matrix material is mainly loaded and therefore the delamination resistance, the interlaminar shear strength and the peeling resistance are low.

In the past a lot of investigations have been made to manufacture three-dimensional reinforcing textiles. Examples for this textiles are multi-layered fabrics, knitted structures for the production of sandwich panels and three-dimensional braids. They all have a three-dimensional geometry and a three-dimensional fibre architecture. Using these textiles for the production of single parts or structures leads to high mechanical properties in z-direction which are caused by three-dimensional fibre orientation. The in-plane properties are reduced by some fibres of the x-y-plane guided into z-direction. Additionally this textiles must often be joined to flat structures. One prominent example for this are stringer stiffened panels. The joining of two different composites structures is often done by adhesives. Therefore the joining zone is non-reinforced again and its properties in z-direction are low. For the optimal transmission of loads from one structure to the other the joining zone should content reinforcements which might be loaded by shear and peeling loads. For manufacturing such reinforcements, stitching is a suitable process. The reinforcing textiles should be stitched together before the wetting process.

Manufacturing complex shapes from conventional (2-D) reinforcing textiles means that every single one has to be draped and deformed. The preforming of several layers in advance is difficult because the single layers are slipping. Stitching is a good alternative for a fixation of single layers. Additionally by a combination of stitching and folding processes new 3-D preforms might be manufactured which are reinforced in discrete regions by the reinforcing sewing thread and the handling properties of the preform are improved by this fixation.

Therefore several investigations are described in literature for an improvement of these mechanical properties by stitching reinforcing textiles. Some other advantages of stitched joining zones might be mentioned. Bonded joining zones which are manufactured by an adhesive are influenced by temperature. Most adhesives are getting soft by increasing temperature and their brittleness increases rapidly with decreasing temperature. They may show their best mechanical properties only in a very narrow range of temperature. Using stitching as a joining method the properties in the joining zone are changed by the temperature in the same way as in-plane.

The use of adhesives to join two composite parts means that the separate parts have to be prepared for the bonding process. The quality of a bonded joining area depends on the thickness of the bonding zone. Bonding together two plain parts will not cause any problems, but if the separate parts are curved it is necessary to manufacture these two parts with exactly

the same curvature. This is not always possible. During stitching the textiles are fixed together before the wetting process. They might be bended after the stitching process.

But also the stitching process must be controlled for getting highest performing joining zones. Possible control mechanisms are shown in this presentation.

PARAMETERS TO BE CONTROLLED DURING STITCHING REINFORCING TEXTILES

Some parameters might be set for the stitching process at the sewing machine. One very important parameter is the geometry of the needle, but the selection of an useful needle for stitching reinforcing textiles can be done in pre-tests. If we are investigating the parameters of a lock-stitch sewing machine further parameters are the turning speed of the main shaft, the pressure of the presser foot and the tensions of the needle thread and the lower thread.

The range of tensions of the lower thread is very narrow for a non-critical stitching process. The tension of the needle thread influences the position of the knot in z-direction because a equilibrium of forces between both the two thread tensions and the friction with the stitched textile is working. As a result of a very low tension of the needle thread the knot will be positioned at the bottom of the stitched textile. At a very high tension of the needle thread the knot will lay on top of the stitched textile. Despite the fact that the position of the knots for clothing textiles is only an asthetical aspect, it is very important for technical textiles, especially reinforcing textiles. The position of the thread will influence the mechanical properties of the whole composite part.

A suitable pressure of the presser foot influences the trouble-free tightening of the knot. As the knot is tightened during the upward movement of the needle, it is important to prevent an upward displacement of the top layers. That is done by the presser foot, too. At lock-stitch sewing machines the pressure is also necessary for a reliable transport of the stitched textiles which is responsible for regular stitch-lengths. Therefore the pressure is also in general an important parameter for stitching. This pressure is suitable for a compression of the reinforcing textiles during the stitching process.

During the consolidation process additionally a compression of the reinforcing textiles happens. It is possible to calculate the thickness t [mm] of the composite by knowledge of the areal weight of a reinforcing textile m_a [g/m²], the aimed fibre volume fraction of the composite to be manufactured φ_F , the density of the fibre material ρ_F [g/cm³] and the number of layers of the reinforcing textile with help of equation 1.

$$t = \frac{n * m_a}{\rho_F * \varphi_F * 1000} \quad (1)$$

If the reinforcing textiles are compressed during stitching to a thickness which is bigger than t the reinforcing sewing thread might be crimped during the consolidation process. Thereby it loses its load bearing architecture (see figure 1). If the pressure is too high the structure of the composite will be deeply disturbed in the area of the stitching row (see also figure 1). From this point of view it is not important to control the pressure itself but its effect concerning the thickness of the stitched textile.

Fig. 1: Effects of different pressures on composite structures

MEASUREMENT OF THE PARAMETERS DURING THE STITCHING PROCESS

For the measurement of the above described parameters a measurement device has been adapted at a lock-stitch sewing machine. An incremental optical encoder has been mounted on the main shaft. Its output signal is a rectangular voltage between 0 and 5 V. It has a resolution of 480 partitions. That means that at every turning angle of 0.75° of the main shaft a measurement of the parameters is triggered.

The lock-stitch sewing machine possesses a triple feed system (unison feed). Besides the drop feed the needle movement describes an elliptical curve. That means that the needle supports the feeding action by the feed-synchronized needle motion. Additionally a top feed is installed, which consists of two presser feet. One of these feet moves only upwards and downwards, the other one moves up and down and additionally in the horizontal direction. Therefore this is the third transport mechanism of the stitching machine. The movement of the presser feet happens in an alternating way. Therefore the textile is always in contact with at least one presser foot, and is always compressed. One of the presser feet rests on the needle plate, the other one on the drop feed if no textile is stitched. During stitching a textile the distance between the presser feet and the needle plate respectively the drop feed is the thickness of this textile loaded by the presser feet. The unison transport is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Unison feed of the used lock-stitch sewing machine

At each presser foot a distance encoder has been fixed. Their signal is set to zero if the presser feet are resting on the needle plate or the drop feed. With the textile between the presser feet and the drop feed respectively the needle plate the thickness of the compressed textile is measured. The measurement of the thickness is triggered by the signals of the incremental optical encoder. That means that 480 signals are derived from each presser foot per turn of the main shaft of the sewing machine respectively per stitch cycle. They are on-line stored and analysed by a computer. They are also set in relation to the turning angle of the main shaft. The sensors possess also a very high resolution. It is possible to measure differences smaller than one micron.

A RES measurement device is integrated in the run of the needle thread. It is responsible for the measurement of the needle thread tension. The measurement of the needle thread tension is also triggered by the incremental optical encoder and the signals are set in relation to the turning angle of the main shaft of the machine.

A schematic view of the measurement systems is shown in figure 3. The systems allow the control of the parameters as well as the reproduction of settings of the machine. Both aspects allow the assessment of the quality during stitching reinforcing textiles for composites. This is shown in an example in the following paragraph.

Figure 3: Schematic view of the measurement system

If 18 layers of a woven glass fabric with an areal weight of

$$m_a = 163 \text{ g/m}^2 \quad (2)$$

should be used for the production of a composite the fibre volume fraction might be assumed as

$$\varphi_F = 50 \% . \quad (3)$$

With this the thickness of the resulting composite can be calculated as

$$t = 2.3 \text{ mm} . \quad (4)$$

Therefore the pressure of the presser feet should be fixed in a way that the textile layers are compressed to a thickness of 2.3 mm during the stitching process. The measurement of the thickness during the stitching process has never been done before, but it is a convenient method to measure a very important parameter during the process.

The measurement of the tension of the needle thread is also important for the quality assessment during stitching reinforcing textiles. It might be a parameter which is important for later calculations of the mechanical properties of the composites. Both measurements are shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Measurement of presser feet distances from the needle plate and needle thread tensions

The needle thread tension is also responsible for thread damages. For this reason the measurement of the tension is important.

MEASUREMENT OF THREAD DAMAGES

Up to now it was not possible to evaluate exactly the thread damages occurring during the stitching process. As in stitching clothing textiles typically polyester threads are used which are not very brittle this topic is not as relevant there as in stitching reinforcing textiles. Using a carbon or glass thread during stitching reinforcing textiles can cause thread damages because of their high brittleness and the small bending curvatures combined with the abrasive-loads which are working on the threads during the stitching process.

It is not possible to dissect the thread out of the stitched textile and do some tensile tests with it. During the preparation of this tests additional damages are caused. It is not possible to determine the amount of this damages.

The needle thread carries the highest loads at a lock-stitch sewing machine. The thread passes the needle hole many times before it is brought into the seam. The aim was to design a test stand at which the loads are simulated.

At a sewing machine with a drop feed the needle thread is teared off the bobbin during the feeding movement. The drawing off is induced by the movement of the stitched textile. This happens when the needle is above the needle plate. At a sewing machine with an unison feed the drawing off also happens during the feeding of the textile, but then the needle actually penetrates the textile. No relative movements between the textile and the thread occur, because the needle and the thread are moving in the same direction with the same velocity. The feeding happens during a defined turning angle of the sewing machine. First it is important to know this angle during which the feeding happens.

To copy all the brakes and all the machine parts which are in friction with the thread and bending it would be very complex. Therefore a drawing off system was adapted to the lock-stitch sewing machine.

The thread passes all machine parts like in the usual stitching process. The process is done without a lower thread. That means that the small friction between the needle thread and the lower thread is not considered. The needle and the needle thread are not passing a textile which is fed by the machine but the needle thread is guided to a bobbin. The bobbin turns with the same velocity and about the same length like the textile would be fed by the unison feed. That means that the drawing off of the bobbin and relative movements between the needle thread and the machine parts are completely the same like during stitching a textile. That moment at which the drawing off starts is given by a signal of the incremental optical encoder. A computer takes this signal as a triggering and outputs a signal to a stepping motor. This stepping motor is connected with a bobbin which takes the thread on. The system is shown schematic in figure 5.

Figure 5: Take up mechanism for the sewing threads loaded during the sewing process

With the thread which is wound on the bobbin tensional tests can be performed. The measured tensile strength is a sign for the filament damages of the sewing thread. With this results the stitching parameters and especially the needle thread tension might be optimized to perform a stitching process with as low as possible filament damages of the sewing thread. This investigations are necessary to make use of the full performance of the threads.

The investigations have been done with a glass filament thread with a total fineness of 138 tex. In these tests the sewing machine ran with a speed of 180 tpm. Higher speeds are possible. The measurement of the needle thread tension is similar to that shown in figure 4. The statistical results of the tensile tests are given in table 1.

Table 1: Tensile strengths of loaded and non-loaded glass filament sewing thread, sewing machine speed for loading the thread: 180 tpm

	thread non-loaded	thread loaded during stitching process
tensile strength [N]	60,72	47,21
standard deviation [N]	4,75	5,06

The results documented in table 1 show that a damage of the glass filament sewing thread occurs. Even with the very low turning speed of 180 tpm the damage occurs. With higher turning speeds and other stitch lengths more damages will occur.

POSITIVE NEEDLE THREAD FEED

The used sewing threads are typically manufactured from reinforcing filaments. They are wound on bigger bobbins than typical sewing threads, e.g. polyester sewing threads. The yarns are very slippery. Therefore their single windings are falling down if the bobbin is placed vertically for the sewing process. Filament damages and a wide range of needle thread tensions are the results. Covering the bobbin with a cloth prevents the falling down of the single windings, but the needle thread tension changes thereby in a very wide range depending on the actual position of the thread. Therefore a mechanism was developed in which the bobbin is placed horizontally on the shaft of a stepping motor. During each stitching cycle the stepping motor turns as far as needle thread is necessary for a perfect performance of the stitch. Thereby the tension of the needle thread is always the same during all stitching cycles.

The positive needle thread feed is a similar system to the mechanism which draws on the needle thread as described before. Its development is a result of the investigations which are done with the measurement systems and reduces thread damages. Therefore it belongs to the area of quality assessment methods during stitching.

CONCLUSIONS

The presented measurement systems are a new and necessary way to improve the quality of composites manufactured from stitched reinforcing textiles. They allow to set the sewing

machine in an optimal way to produce composites with load bearing structures of the sewing threads. They also allow to reproduce the settings of a machine and to show correlations between the stitching parameters and the mechanical properties of the composites.

With the measurement of thread damages a new method has been developed which gives the possibility to examine the properties of sewing threads after the stitching process. This has not been necessary in the area of clothing textiles because of the low brittleness of the sewing threads. Using now glass and carbon threads for the stitching process makes the new information useful. Especially for the calculations or simulations of the mechanical properties of stitched joining zones in a composite it is necessary to assume the mechanical properties of the sewing thread.

This shows that the typical measurement systems of textile technology might be useful for new results in stitching reinforcing textiles for composites.

The paper gives an overview over the methods used for the improvement of the properties of composites manufactured of stitched reinforcing textiles. First tests with the systems have been done. The complete results will be shown during the oral presentation of the paper.

REFERENCES

1. Mignery, L.A., Tan, L.M., Sun, C.T.: The use of stitching to suppress delamination in laminated composites. Johnson, W.S. (ed.): Delamination and Debonding of Materials, ASTM STP 876, Philadelphia/USA: ASTM, 1985, 371-385.
2. Sawyer, J.W.: Effects of stitching on the strength of bonded composite single lap joints. AIAA Journal 23 (1985), 1744-1748.
3. Portanova, M.A., Poe, C.C., Whitcomb, J.D.: Open hole and post-impact compression fatigue of stitched and unstitched carbon/epoxy composites. NASA TM 102676, 1990
4. Du, X., Xue, F., Gu, Z.: Experimental study of the effect of stitching on strength of a composite laminate. International Symposium on Composite Materials and Structures (Beijing 10-13/06/1986). Proc., Lancaster/PA/USA: Technomic, 1986, 912-918
5. Liu, D., Kim, Y.G., Hong, S.: Stitching as joint in woven composite plate. ASM/ED: 3rd Annual ASM/ESD Adv. Comp. Conf. (Detroit/MI/USA 15-17/09/1987), 343-347
6. Matsuhisha, Y., Hiramatsu, T., Nishimara, A: Z-directional laminate reinforcing material. High performance Torayca carbon stitching thread. SAMPE: 33rd Int. SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition (Anaheim 07-10/03/1988)
7. Herszberg, I., Bannister, M.K.: Tensile properties of thin stitched carbon/epoxy composites. Cooperative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures: 5th Australian Aerospace Conference (09/1989), Proc. ACN 059048770, Victoria: CRC-AS Ltd., 1993

8. Herszberg, I., Bannister, M.K.: Compression and compression-after-impact properties of thin stitched carbon/epoxy composites. Cooperative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures: 5th Australian Aerospace Conference (09/1989), Proc. ACN 059048770, Victoria: CRC-AS Ltd., 1993
9. Mc Illhagger, R., Hill, B.J., McLaughlin, P.: Flexural properties of sewn carbon-fibre composites. Journal of the Textile Institute 83 (1992), 614-620